

First approach towards some novel macrocyclic complexes having mixed ligands : synthesis, characterization, catalytic and antimicrobial aspects of some nickel(II) macrocyclic complexes having tetraoxotetraazathio ligands in 24-28 membered rings^ψ

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Alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of nickel(II), having potential donors N_4S_4 of the general

formula, $[Ni(L)\{S_2P(O)G\}_2]$ (where L = macrocyclic ligands L^1, L^2 and L^3 and $G = CH_3-\overset{|}{C}-\overset{|}{C}-CH_3, (CH_3)_2-\overset{|}{C}-\overset{|}{C}-(CH_3)_2,$

$(CH_3)_2\overset{|}{C}-CH_2-\overset{|}{C}-\overset{|}{C}-CH_2-C(CH_3)_2-\overset{|}{C}-CH_2$ and $\overset{|}{C}-CH_2-C(C_2H_5)_2-\overset{|}{C}-CH_2$ have been synthesized from the reactions of $[Ni(L)X_2]$ (where X = Cl, NO_3 or CH_3COO) with ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates in 1 : 2 molar ratios in THF. These complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, molecular weight determinations, IR, ^{31}P NMR, electronic spectra and magnetic measurements. Molecular weight determinations of these complexes indicates their monomeric nature. Octahedral structures have been proposed on the basis of ^{31}P NMR, electronic spectra and magnetic measurements in which four nitrogen atoms of the macrocyclic ring coordinate to the central nickel ion in square-planar geometry and each dithiophosphate moiety occupies the axial positions binding the central nickel ion in a unidentate manner. Out of twenty one newly synthesized complexes, ten were tested for their catalytic activity, and all the ten complexes were found to be effective catalyst for the oxidation of thiol and benzyl alcohol. The anti-microbial activities of these derivatives have been studied by screening them against fungi like *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Trichoderma harzianum* and bacteria like *S. typhi* and *B. subtili*. The alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives were found to be more fungitoxic and antibacterial than their corresponding macrocyclic complexes.

Due to importance in biological systems, as a synthetic model for many metalloenzyme reactions¹⁻³, their novel structural features and unusual magnetic properties, there has been considerable interest in the transition metal chemistry in the mixed ligand compounds during last few years⁴⁻¹⁵. Recently, a number of mixed ligand complexes involving Ni^{II} with sulphur containing ligand have been reported and their structures have been confirmed by single crystal X-Ray crystallography¹⁶⁻²⁰. On the other hand macrocyclic complexes of both transition and non-transition elements have received considerable interest during last one and a half decades due to their wide diversity in chemical²¹⁻²⁸ and biological²⁹⁻³¹. Macrocyclic complexes having tetraaza³²⁻³⁶, dioxotetraaza^{37,38}, tetraoxo-tetraaza³⁹, tetraoxooctaaza⁴⁰ and trioxotetraaza⁴¹ are well reported. Recently, we have reported synthesis, characterization and biocidal screening of some new thioaaza macrocyclic com-

plexes of Ni^{II} ^{42,43}. In spite of vast innovations in macrocyclic chemistry and tremendous interest in mixed ligand complexes, no macrocyclic complex having mixed ligand system has been reported so far. Alkylene dithiophosphates has been the area of our thrust since last many years^{44,55}. Recently, first time, we have reported the synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial aspects of the mixed ligand macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} having dialkyl- and alkylene dithiophosphate moieties having N_2S_2 potential donors in 14-20 membered rings^{54,55}. In continuation to the above we hereby report the synthesis, characterization, catalytic and antimicrobial aspects of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} in which four nitrogen atoms of the macrocyclic ring coordinate to the central nickel ion in the square-planar form and each dithiophosphate moiety occupies the axial positions binding the central nickel ion in a unidentate manner through strong electrostatic attraction.

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Results and discussion

Reaction of nickel salts with bis-(2-aminophenyl)-disulphide and dicarboxylic acids in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios in methanol takes place in the following manner :

$n = 3, 4$ or $(\text{CH}_2)_n = o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3$ or CH_3COO

Fig. 1. General structure of macrocyclic complexes derived by the template condensation of bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide and dicarboxylic acids in the presence of nickel salts.

The above macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} in THF were reacted with a methanolic solution of ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates in 1 : 2 molar ratios to afford the alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of the macrocyclic Ni^{II} complexes in the following manner :

$\text{G} = \text{CH}_3\text{-CH-CH-CH}_3, (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C-C(CH}_3)_2, (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C-CH}_2\text{-CH-CH}_2, \text{CH}_2\text{-C(CH}_3)_2\text{-CH}_2$ and $\text{CH}_2\text{-C(C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{-CH}_2$,

$\text{L} =$ macrocyclic ligands L^1, L^2 and L^3 ; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{CH}_3\text{CHOO}$, $\text{L}^1 =$ macrocyclic ligand derived from bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide and glutaric acid ($n = 3$), $\text{L}^2 =$ macrocyclic ligand derived from bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide and adipic acid ($n = 4$), $\text{L}^3 =$ macrocyclic ligand derived from bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide and phthalic acid ($(\text{CH}_2)_n = o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$).

The derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of the following alkylene dithiophosphoric acids have been synthesized. Their trivial name as well as their IUPAC names have been given below. IUPAC names have been mentioned in

parenthesis.

- | | |
|--|---|
| $\text{HS}_2\overline{\text{POCH(CH}_3)_2\text{CH(CH}_3)_2\text{O}}$ | Butylene dithiophosphoric acid |
| (2-mercapto-2-thiono-4,5-dimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaphospholane) | |
| $\text{HS}_2\overline{\text{POC(CH}_3)_2\text{C(CH}_3)_2\text{O}}$ | Tetramethylethylene/Pinacolene dithiophosphoric acid |
| (2-mercapto-2-thiono-4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaphospholane) | |
| $\text{HS}_2\overline{\text{POC(CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH(CH}_3)_2\text{O}}$ | Hexylene dithiophosphoric acid |
| (2-mercapto-2-thiono-4,4,6-trimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphorinane) | |
| $\text{HS}_2\overline{\text{POCH}_2\text{C(CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}}$ | Neo-pentylene-(2,2-dimethylpropylene)-dithiophosphoric acid |
| (2-mercapto-2-thiono-5,5-dimethyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphorinane) | |
| $\text{HS}_2\overline{\text{POCCH}_2\text{C(C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}}$ | 2,2-Diethylpropylene-dithiophosphoric acid |
| (2-mercapto-2-thiono-5,5-diethyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphorinane) | |

The reaction mixture was refluxed for *ca.* 4 h. On cooling the crystals of the dithiophosphate derivatives separated out.

Except for THF and DMSO, these derivatives are insoluble in common organic solvents. All derivatives are dull, shiny or pinkish-green solids and melt with decomposition at high temperature (204–229°C). Molecular weight determinations indicate their monomeric nature (Table 1). The analytical data of these derivatives are given in Table 1. The molar conductance of 10^{-3} M solutions in DMSO lie in the range $3.8\text{--}6.8 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ showing that these complexes are non-electrolyte (Table 1).

Infrared spectra :

In the macrocyclic complexes, the four bands in the regions $1680\text{--}1640(\text{m}), 1595\text{--}1560(\text{s}), 1275\text{--}1262(\text{m})$ and $680\text{--}640(\text{w}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been ascribed to the amide I, amide II, amide III and amide IV in-plane deformation vibrations, respectively⁵⁶. A broad band in the region $3240\text{--}3150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to the $\nu(\text{NH})$ vibration of the secondary amino group. These bands do not show any significant change from their parent macrocyclic complexes⁴³. Two bands present in the regions $1070\text{--}1040$ and $890\text{--}855$

Table 1. Analytical and physico-chemical data of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} containing tetraoxotetrahydrothetraza ligands (1-21)

Compd.	Analyses % :				Conductivity Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1})	M.p. (decomp.) $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)		Magnetic moment μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectra λ_{max} (nm)	^{31}P NMR chemical shift (δ)	
	C	H	N	P			S	Ni				(Calcd.)
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POCH(CH ₃) ₂ CH(CH ₃)O) ₂ (C ₄₂ H ₄₈ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	45.08 (45.29)	4.26 (4.31)	5.12 (5.03)	5.84 (5.57)	23.29 (23.00)	5.19 (5.27)	5.19 (5.27)	212	1126.8 (1112.7)	3.20 (26.7)	410 (41.8)	92.08 (95.49)
(1)												
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POC(CH ₃) ₂ C(CH ₃) ₂ O) ₂ (C ₄₆ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	47.08 (47.23)	4.65 (4.79)	4.98 (4.79)	5.21 (5.30)	22.14 (21.90)	5.12 (5.02)	5.12 (5.02)	208	1182.4 (1168.7)	3.08 (28.5)	420 (39.8)	95.56 (93.07)
(2)												
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POC(CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)O) ₂ (C ₄₆ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	47.76 (47.23)	4.88 (4.79)	4.62 (4.79)	5.74 (5.30)	21.52 (21.90)	5.11 (5.02)	5.11 (5.02)	204	1150.4 (1168.7)	3.12 (24.8)	420 (39.8)	77.67 (73.20)
(3)												
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POCH ₂ C(CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ (C ₄₄ H ₅₂ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	46.82 (46.28)	4.35 (4.55)	4.76 (4.90)	5.18 (5.43)	22.56 (22.44)	5.21 (5.14)	5.21 (5.14)	218	1122.2 (1140.7)	3.04 (30.6)	410 (41.6)	74.96 (78.58)
(4)												
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POCH ₂ C(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ CH ₂ O) ₂ (C ₄₈ H ₆₀ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	48.37 (48.13)	5.13 (5.01)	4.54 (4.67)	5.26 (5.18)	21.54 (21.39)	4.78 (4.90)	4.78 (4.90)	216	1183.4 (1196.7)	3.12 (25.7)	400 (43.8)	–
(5)												
[Ni(L ¹)Cl ₂] C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ NiO ₄ S ₄ Cl ₂ ^c	49.79 (49.87)	3.84 (3.91)	6.78 (6.84)	–	15.48 (15.64)	7.08 (7.17)	7.08 (7.17)	238	833.4 (817.7)	3.08 (24.2)	410 (41.8)	–
(6)												
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POC(CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)O) ₂ (C ₄₆ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	47.18 (47.23)	4.65 (4.79)	4.64 (4.79)	5.44 (5.30)	21.78 (21.90)	5.06 (5.02)	5.06 (5.02)	214	1182.3 (1168.7)	3.18 (26.5)	450 (41.0)	71.25 (73.20)
(7)												
[Ni(L ¹)](NO ₃) ₂ C ₃₄ H ₃₂ N ₄ NiO ₄ S ₄ (NO ₃) ₂ ^d	46.69 (46.85)	3.62 (3.67)	9.68 (9.64)	–	14.57 (14.70)	6.68 (6.74)	6.68 (6.74)	218	888.4 (870.7)	3.18 (30.8)	410 (41.2)	–
(8)												
[Ni(L ¹)](S ₂ POC(CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ CH(CH ₃)O) ₂ (C ₄₆ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ Ni)	47.44 (47.23)	4.68 (4.79)	4.88 (4.79)	5.42 (5.30)	21.73 (21.90)	5.12 (5.02)	5.12 (5.02)	224	1110.4 (1168.7)	3.08 (25.4)	400 (44.2)	–
(9)												

Table-I (contd.)

$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^1)(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	52.58	4.47	6.32	-	15.08	6.68	4.2	228	878.8	3.12	630	410	-
$\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4\text{S}_4(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2^a$	(52.73)	(4.39)	(6.47)		(14.80)	(6.78)			(864.7)		(30.4)	(40.8)	
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POCH}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{O}\}_2]$	46.04	4.48	4.82	5.51	22.52	5.15	3.8	218	1122.6	2.98	655	420	98.18
$(\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{52}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(46.28)	(4.55)	(4.90)	(5.43)	(22.44)	(5.14)			(1140.7)		(24.4)	(41.8)	(95.49)
(8)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POC}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}\}_2]$	48.38	4.94	4.69	5.27	21.26	4.78	4.2	229	1209.6	3.14	660	405	76.68
$(\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{60}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(48.13)	(5.01)	(4.67)	(5.18)	(21.39)	(4.90)			(1196.7)		(28.8)	(42.9)	(78.58)
(9)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POC}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)\text{O}\}_2]$	48.29	5.04	4.57	5.27	21.21	4.79	5.6	220	1172.3	3.18	650	470	-
$(\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{60}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(48.13)	(5.01)	(4.67)	(5.18)	(21.39)	(4.90)			(1196.7)		(26.5)	(41.4)	
(10)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POCH}_2(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}\}_2]$	47.44	4.72	4.81	5.28	21.82	5.06	6.2	224	1152.8	3.20	665	420	97.84
$(\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{56}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(47.23)	(4.79)	(4.79)	(5.30)	(21.90)	(5.02)			(1168.7)		(25.6)	(40.4)	(95.49)
(11)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}\}_2]$	48.74	5.31	4.52	5.13	20.83	4.85	5.8	220	1242.6	3.06	670	420	-
$(\text{C}_{50}\text{H}_{64}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(48.99)	(5.22)	(4.57)	(5.06)	(20.90)	(4.79)			(1224.7)		(27.4)	(41.2)	
(12)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\text{Cl}_2]$	50.97	4.24	6.52	-	15.18	6.88	4.6	216	832.4	3.18	680	400	-
$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4\text{S}_4\text{Cl}_2^a$	(51.08)	(4.25)	(6.62)		(15.13)	(6.94)			(845.7)		(29.8)	(44.4)	
(13)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}\}_2]$	47.73	4.84	4.65	5.21	21.38	5.10	5.8	223	1152.6	2.98	670	450	80.23
$(\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{56}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(47.23)	(4.79)	(4.79)	(5.30)	(21.90)	(5.02)			(1168.7)		(27.6)	(42.8)	(78.58)
(14)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	48.18	4.08	9.18	-	14.11	6.46	5.2	218	886.8	3.12	630	410	-
$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4\text{S}_4(\text{NO}_3)_2^a$	(48.06)	(4.00)	(9.34)		(14.24)	(6.53)			(898.7)		(30.8)	(41.2)	
(15)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)\{\text{S}_2\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}\}_2]$	47.42	4.77	4.82	5.33	22.08	5.06	4.8	210	1152.2	3.08	660	415	74.34
$(\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{56}\text{N}_4\text{P}_2\text{S}_8\text{O}_8\text{Ni})$	(47.23)	(4.79)	(4.79)	(5.30)	(21.90)	(5.02)			(1168.7)		(29.8)	(43.6)	(78.58)
(16)													
$[\text{Ni}(\text{L}^2)(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$	53.66	4.68	6.32	-	14.48	6.59	3.8	230	880.4	3.04	670	450	-
$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{36}\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_4\text{S}_4(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2^a$	(53.75)	(4.70)	(6.27)		(14.33)	(6.57)			(892.7)		(26.9)	(42.2)	

Table-1 (contd.)

[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POCH(CH ₃) ₂ CH(CH ₃ O)] ₂ (C ₄₈ H ₄₄ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (15)	48.64 (48.78)	3.65 (3.72)	4.70 (4.74)	5.34 (5.25)	21.53 (21.68)	4.78 (4.97)	4.3	221	1164.2 (1180.7)	3.20	650 (25.8)	410 (39.6)	91.22 (95.49)
[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POC(CH ₃) ₂ C(CH ₃ O)] ₂ (C ₅₂ H ₅₂ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (16)	50.38 (50.45)	4.16 (4.20)	4.48 (4.52)	5.06 (5.01)	20.56 (20.70)	4.61 (4.74)	4.6	218	1251.2 (1236.7)	3.04	665 (25.4)	400 (43.9)	-
[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POC(CH ₃) ₂ CH(CH ₃ O)] ₂ (C ₅₂ H ₅₂ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (17)	50.54 (50.45)	4.14 (4.20)	4.58 (4.52)	5.06 (5.01)	20.62 (20.70)	4.69 (4.74)	4.2	228	1204.6 (1236.7)	3.12	680 (26.8)	400 (43.2)	-
[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POCH ₂ C(CH ₃) ₂ CH ₂ O)] ₂ (C ₅₀ H ₄₈ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (18)	50.54 (49.64)	3.89 (3.97)	4.58 (4.63)	5.22 (5.12)	21.39 (21.17)	4.87 (4.85)	5.7	219	1254.2 (1208.7)	3.16	680 (26.8)	400 (43.4)	80.11 (78.58)
[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POCH ₂ C(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ CH ₂ O)] ₂ (C ₅₄ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (19)	51.17 (51.23)	4.39 (4.42)	4.47 (4.42)	4.88 (4.90)	20.38 (20.24)	4.78 (4.64)	5.1	224	1236.8 (1264.7)	3.08	655 (26.8)	420 (39.8)	-
[Ni(L ³)Cl ₂] C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₄ NiO ₄ S ₄ Cl ₂ ^d (20)	54.22 (54.19)	3.22 (3.16)	6.24 (6.32)	-	14.28 (14.44)	6.70 (6.62)	4.4	227	874.2 (885.7)	3.12	660 (29.4)	415 (42.6)	-
[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POCH ₂ C(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ CH ₂ O)] ₂ (C ₅₄ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (21)	51.07 (51.23)	4.51 (4.42)	4.30 (4.42)	4.84 (4.90)	20.47 (20.24)	4.38 (4.64)	6.8	218	1245.9 (1264.7)	3.18	670 (26.9)	410 (42.2)	-
[Ni(L ³)(NO ₃) ₂] C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₄ NiO ₄ S ₄ (NO ₃) ₂ ^d (22)	51.34 (51.13)	3.01 (2.98)	8.88 (8.94)	-	13.74 (13.63)	6.12 (6.25)	4.6	234	926.4 (938.7)	3.08	655 (26.6)	410 (39.2)	-
[Ni(L ³)] ₂ [S ₂ POCH ₂ C(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ CH ₂ O)] ₂ (C ₅₄ H ₅₆ N ₄ P ₂ S ₈ O ₈ .Ni) (23)	51.07 (51.23)	4.51 (4.42)	4.30 (4.42)	4.84 (4.90)	20.47 (20.24)	4.38 (4.64)	3.8	219	1234.6 (1264.7)	2.98	660 (28.4)	410 (42.0)	-
[Ni(L ³)(CH ₃ COO) ₂] C ₄₀ H ₂₈ N ₄ NiO ₄ S ₄ (CH ₃ COO) ₂ ^d (24)	56.42 (56.60)	3.56 (3.64)	6.14 (6.00)	-	13.56 (13.72)	6.33 (6.29)	3.8	228	918.8 (932.7)	3.14	630 (24.8)	410 (39.8)	-

^dAnalytical and physico-chemical data of precursor macrocyclic complexes.

cm^{-1} may be assigned to (P)–O–C and P–O–(C) stretching vibrations, respectively⁵⁷. The bands present between 1000–950 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the ring vibrations of dioxaphospholanes and dioxaphosphorinanes respectively, which are probably coupled with C–C stretching vibrations^{58,59}. A strong band present in the region 700–670 cm^{-1} , which also appears in ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates at around the same region, is attributed to the free P=S moiety. This indicates the unidentate behaviour of the dithiophosphate moieties^{60,61}. The presence of sharp bands in the region 470–410 cm^{-1} and 377–318 cm^{-1} have been assigned to $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Ni-S})$ vibrations, respectively⁴⁷.

³¹P NMR spectra :

Due to the paramagnetic nature of Ni^{II} in an octahedral geometry, the ¹H NMR spectra of its complexes cannot be observed as easily as those of diamagnetic Ni^{II} complexes. We have reported earlier the ¹H NMR of some paramagnetic Ni^{II} complexes^{46,47}. During the present investigations it was not possible to obtain the ¹H NMR spectra for the present complexes.

³¹P NMR spectra of a few compounds could be recorded, however. The spectra were recorded on a 270 MHz spectrometer using CDCl_3 as a solvent and H_3PO_4 as an external standard. As we reported earlier^{46,47}, the position of the ³¹P chemical shift is not influenced by the paramagnetic nature of the nickel ion. The values of chemical shifts of the newly synthesized compounds are reported in Table 1. The chemical shift values do not show any significant change from their parent alkylene dithiophosphoric acids. This indicates again the monodentate nature of alkylene dithiophosphate moieties attached to the central nickel ion^{60,61}.

Electronic spectra :

Electronic spectra were recorded on a GBC 911 spectrophotometer in the range of 380–1000 nm using THF as a solvent. Only two bands, ν_2 and ν_3 , were observed at around 630–690 (ϵ : 24.2–26.8) and 400–430 (ϵ : 39.2–43.8) nm; which may be attributed to the $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(F)$ and $3A_{2g} \rightarrow 3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively. These transitions indicate the six-coordination of the central nickel atom⁶².

Magnetic susceptibility :

The magnetic moments of the dithiophosphate derivatives are given in Table 1. The magnetic susceptibility was measured by a Faraday balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{CNS})_4]$ as calibrant. Pascal constants were used for diamagnetic corrections. The complexes show magnetic moment values

of 2.98–3.20 B.M. at room temperature, which correspond to two unpaired electrons, as expected for Ni^{II} complexes⁶³. Data are given in Table 1.

Structural information :

The above spectral and magnetic data indicate the octahedral geometry shown in Fig. 2 for the above derivatives in which four nitrogen atoms of the macrocyclic ring coordinate to the central nickel ion in square-planar geometry and each dithiophosphate moiety occupies the axial positions binding to the central nickel ion in a unidentate manner through strong electrostatic attraction.

$$n = 3, 4 \text{ or } (\text{CH}_2)_n = o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}$$

Fig. 2. Tentative structure of the alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} (1-21).

Catalytic activity :

During last two decades much work has been reported on the structural aspects of macrocyclic complexes. A few scattered reports on the catalytic activity of macrocyclic complexes appear in the literature⁶⁴. However, they have reported the use of macrocyclic complexes of cobalt only for the oxidation of thiols. According to their studies nickel(II) macrocyclic complexes don't catalyze the oxidation of thiols. Considering the potential use of macrocyclic

complexes as a catalyst we have observed the catalytic activity of ten newly synthesized complexes. During the present investigations macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} have been proved to be effective catalyst for the oxidation of thiols and benzyl alcohol. The catalytic effect of macrocyclic complexes for the oxidation of thiol has been shown to yield 45–70% of disulphide. The results obtained for oxidation of benzyl alcohol to benzaldehyde, by the macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} were found to be 45 to 75%. At room temperature no catalytic effect was observed. However on refluxing the benzyl alcohol, the higher catalytic effect was observed. The results for the catalytic oxidation of thiol

and benzyl alcohol, by the macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II}, are given in Table 2.

Antimicrobial activity :

The antimicrobial activity of bis-(2-aminophenyl)-disulphide, dicarboxylic acids, nickel salts and the precursor macrocyclic complexes (L¹ to L³) has been reported in our earlier communication⁴³.

Like their precursor macrocyclic complexes, the antifungal activity of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives has been tested against three fungi, namely *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Trichoderma harzianum*. The screening data for the average percentage inhibition of the fungi at 100, 125 and 200 ppm concentrations are given in Table 3. The values obtained suggest that the alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes are more fungitoxic than their precursor macrocyclic complexes as well as the alkylene dithiophosphoric acids. Further, the data also indicate that with the increase in the concentration, the fungitoxicity also increases.

The antibacterial activity against two bacteria namely *S. typhi* and *B. subtili* were tested by the inhibition zone technique⁶⁵. The data obtained are presented in Table 4. The values suggest that the alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of the macrocyclic complexes are more antibacterial than their precursor macrocyclic complexes (NiL¹-NiL³). Of course, the dithiophosphate moieties behave as a monodentate in all the derivatives, but substitution of anions (Cl, NO₃ and CH₃COO) by the dithiophosphate moi-

Table 2. Catalytic activities of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II}

Compd.	Benzyl alcohol		Compd.	Thiophenol	
	No. of moles of compd. used	Product yield %		No. of moles of compd. used	Product yield %
1	2.2 × 10 ⁻³	56.72	1	3.04 × 10 ⁻³	63.08
3	4.1 × 10 ⁻³	67.82	3	1.48 × 10 ⁻³	48.24
4	2.28 × 10 ⁻³	45.22	4	2.12 × 10 ⁻³	52.34
9	1.24 × 10 ⁻³	67.24	9	4.08 × 10 ⁻³	56.06
10	3.04 × 10 ⁻³	71.82	10	4.11 × 10 ⁻³	60.23
11	1.18 × 10 ⁻³	73.00	11	1.18 × 10 ⁻³	69.84
15	3.14 × 10 ⁻³	68.92	15	2.01 × 10 ⁻³	68.12
16	2.98 × 10 ⁻³	70.82	16	1.62 × 10 ⁻³	58.42
17	4.34 × 10 ⁻³	74.89	17	1.26 × 10 ⁻³	70.08
20	3.08 × 10 ⁻³	73.86	20	1.33 × 10 ⁻³	50.34

Table 3. Antifungal activity of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II}

Compd.	Average % of inhibition after 72 h at 30 ± 2°C								
	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>			<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>			<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>		
	100	125	200	100	125	200	100	125	200
1	42	52	66	50	54	60	56	60	63
2	47	51	57	62	65	70	57	61	64
3	47	50	55	48	52	58	60	64	69
4	48	53	61	58	61	65	49	53	60
5	56	60	66	50	54	60	51	55	59
8	59	64	68	52	57	60	50	58	63
9	61	65	67	60	65	69	58	64	68
10	60	65	70	50	54	59	52	60	66
11	58	63	68	52	57	62	63	60	67
12	60	65	68	58	62	67	56	60	40
15	54	56	67	60	64	67	51	54	57
16	59	63	68	58	62	66	47	51	58
17	59	63	67	58	63	67	56	60	63
18	61	65	68	62	65	70	57	61	64
19	60	64	68	58	61	65	58	64	69

eties reduces the polarity of the central atom by partial sharing of its positive charge. Data are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II}

Compd.	Percentage growth inhibition after 24 h at 30 ± 2°C (conc. in ppm)			
	<i>B. subtili</i>		<i>S. typhi</i>	
	500	1000	500	1000
1	17	20	18	18
2	18	22	15	22
3	19	22	18	21
4	18	21	19	21
5	20	22	15	18
8	20	23	19	21
9	19	21	20	22
10	18	21	19	22
11	17	20	19	19
12	19	22	22	24
15	18	22	17	22
16	20	23	19	21
17	20	22	18	22
18	20	23	22	24
19	19	22	20	22

Experimental

All the nickel salts and dicarboxylic acids of A.R. grade were obtained from S.d.-fine chemicals and were used without further purification. *o*-Aminothiophenol was used as obtained from Merck. Solvents were purified and dried by standard methods. The chelating ligand bis-(2-aminophenyl) disulphide was synthesized by the dimerization of *o*-aminothiophenol by H₂O₂ as reported in the literature⁶⁶. Ammonium alkylene dithiophosphates were prepared by the method as we reported in our earlier communication⁴⁴.

Microanalyses for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were determined from SICART, Vallabh Vidyanagar. Nickel and phosphorus were estimated by standard methods⁶⁷. The molecular weights were determined by Rast Camphor method. Infrared data were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer as KBr pellets. Magnetic data were recorded on a Faraday balance. Electronic spectra were recorded on GBC 911 spectrophotometer in the range 380–1000 nm using THF as a solvent. ³¹P NMR spectra were recorded on a Jeol 270 MHz spectrometer using CDCl₃ as a solvent and H₃PO₄ as an external standard.

Synthesis of precursor macrocyclic complexes :

Macrocyclic complex derived from template conden-

sation of glutaric acid and bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide in the presence of nickel chloride : A solution of nickel chloride (0.692 g, 0.0029 mol) in *ca.* 40 ml methanol was reacted with bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide (1.440 g, 0.0058 mol) dissolved in *ca.* 40 ml methanol. This was followed by the addition of a *ca.* 40 ml methanolic solution of glutaric acid (0.769 g, 0.0058 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h. The green precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and dried in vacuum (Found : C, 49.79; H, 3.84; N, 6.78; S, 15.48; Ni, 7.08. Calcd. for C₃₄H₃₂N₄S₂O₄NiCl₂ (fw 817.7) : C, 49.87; H, 3.91; N, 6.84; S, 15.64; Ni, 7.17%) m.p. 238°C; yield 0.922 g (72%); λ_{max}/nm (ε dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) 630 (24.2), 410 (41.8); μ_{eff} = 3.08 B.M.

Macrocyclic complex derived from template condensation of phthalic acid and bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide in the presence of nickel nitrate : A solution of nickel nitrate (0.724 g, 0.0024 mol) in *ca.* 40 ml methanol was reacted with bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide (1.236 g, 0.0049 mol) dissolved in *ca.* 40 ml methanol. This was followed by the addition of a *ca.* 40 ml methanolic solution of phthalic acid (0.828 g, 0.0049 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 10 h. The green precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and dried in vacuum (Found : C, 51.34; H, 3.01; N, 8.84; S, 13.74; Ni, 6.12. Calcd. for C₄₀H₂₈N₄NiO₄S₄(NO₃)₂ (fw 938.7) : C, 51.13; H, 2.98; N, 8.94; S, 13.63; Ni, 6.25%) m.p. 234°C, yield 1.76 g (75%); λ_{max}/nm (ε dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) 630 (24.8), 410 (39.8); μ_{eff} = 3.08 B.M.

Synthesis of alkylene dithiophosphate derivatives of macrocyclic complexes :

Synthesis of butylene dithiophosphate derivative of macrocyclic complex obtained from the reaction of ammonium butylene dithiophosphate with the complex derived by the template condensation of glutaric acid and bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide in the presence of nickel chloride (ML^I) : The precursor macrocyclic complex mentioned above (0.937 g, 0.0014 mol) was dissolved in *ca.* 50 ml THF and was reacted with methanolic solution (*ca.* 50 ml) of ammonium butylene dithiophosphate (0.460 g, 0.0022 mol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 4 h. On cooling the green crystals of the alkylene dithiophosphate derivative separated out and filtered through a G-3 filtering funnel. The product was washed several times with methanol by vigorous shaking in a separation funnel to remove ammonium chloride ions formed during the reaction. The product was dried in vacuum and was crystallized with THF/C₂H₅OH mixture (1 : 1). Compounds 1-5, 8-12 and 15-19 were prepared by the same method.

Synthesis of hexylene dithiophosphate derivative of macrocyclic complex obtained from the reaction of ammonium hexylene dithiophosphate with the complex derived by the template condensation of phthalic acid and bis-(2-aminophenyl)disulphide in the presence of nickel nitrate (ML³) : The precursor macrocyclic complex mentioned above (1.014 g, 0.0010 mol) was dissolved in *ca.* 50 ml THF and was reacted with a methanolic solution (*ca.* 50 ml) of ammonium hexylene dithiophosphate (0.525 g, 0.0021 mol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 4 h. On cooling the green crystals of the dithiophosphate derivative of compound separated out and were filtered through a G-3 filtering funnel. This crude product was washed several times with methanol by vigorous shaking in the filtering funnel, to remove ammonium nitrate formed during the reaction. The product was dried under vacuum and crystallized in THF/C₂H₅OH mixture (1 : 1). Compounds **6**, **13** and **20** were prepared by the same method.

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